

D10.2. OEI - Requirement No. 2

C. Sardeli, Independent Ethics Advisor

Publishable Summary

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ThrombUS+ Consortium

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About ThrombUS+

Deep vein thrombosis (DVT) is the formation of a blood clot within the deep veins, most commonly those of the lower limbs, causing obstruction of blood flow. In 50% of people with DVT, the clot eventually breaks off and travels to the lung to cause pulmonary embolism. Clinical assessment of DVT is notoriously unreliable because up to 2/3 of DVT episodes are clinically silent and patients are symptom free even when pulmonary embolism has developed. Early diagnosis of DVT is crucial and despite the progress made in ultrasound imaging and plethysmography techniques, there is a need for new methods to enable continuous monitoring DVT diagnosis at the point of care.

ThrombUS+ brings together an interdisciplinary team of industrial, technology, regulatory, social science and clinical trial experts to develop a novel wearable diagnostic device for point-of-care, operator free, continuous monitoring in patients with high DVT risk. The device will combine autonomous, AI driven DVT detection based on a novel wearable ultrasound hardware, impedance plethysmography and light reflection rheography for immediate detection of blood clot formation in the lower limb. Activity and other physiological measurements will be used to provide a continuous assessment of DVT risk and support DVT prevention via serious gaming. The aggregated data will drive an intelligence decision support unit that will provide accurate monitoring and alerts. Extended reality will be used to guide experts to design exercises and patients to use the device optimally.

ThrombUS+ is intended for use by postoperative patients in the ward, during long surgical operations, cancer patients or otherwise bedridden patients at home or in care units, and women during pregnancy and postpartum. ThrombUS+ will use big data sets for AI training collected in the project via 3 large scale clinical studies and will validate the outcome in the clinical setting via 1 early feasibility study and 1 multi-centre clinical trial.

Deliverable D10.2 Description

According to the opinions of the ethics experts that evaluated the submitted proposal prior to its funding, the proposal raised several ethics issues. Among others, that the clinical trial C1 requires a continuous DVT monitoring of high-risk patients (postoperative and mostly bedridden), using the ThrombUS+ wearable device, from 12 hours after surgery and for 3 days. This raised questions about the vulnerability of the participants and their autonomy, especially because the applicants missed to indicate participation of vulnerable individuals in Part A Ethics Issues Table. Furthermore, partner PBY was presented as “social sciences expert involved in health technology deployments” to advise on the clinical studies/trials protocols (Section 2 - Preparedness status - in 3 clinical studies and 2 clinical trials descriptions); however, this is a research and consulting firm specialising in data and behavioural science to advise organisations on decision-making processes. Its expertise is not particularly relevant to address issues of autonomy and vulnerability in patients participating in clinical trials.

Due to the abovementioned, it was indicated that the project must appoint an Ethics Advisor with expertise in human-centred technology (AI-powered technology in particular), to help prioritise the well-being of the participants in the clinical trials and studies, to help the project adopt an ethics-by-design approach (rather than a conformity-by-design technical approach) for the development of ThrombUS – ThrombUS+. A report by the ethics advisor must be submitted to cover these issues every year starting at M12.

D10.2 is the publishable summary of the first yearly report compiled by the Independent Ethics Advisor appointed by the Consortium.

Cite this Document as

Sardeli C., ThrombUS+ Ethics Appraisal Report #1, Deliverable D10.2, ThrombUS+ Horizon Europe Innovation Action, EC Grant Agreement No. 101137227, 23 December 2024, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14510676> [publishable summary].

Terms and Definitions

Abbreviation	Definition
DVT	Deep vein thrombosis
EC	European Commission
ENTIS	European Network of Teratology Information Specialists
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HADEA	European Health and Digital Executive Agency
hE	Human Embryos
hESC	Human Embryonic Stem Cells
IMI	Innovative Medicines Initiative
OEI	Other Ethics Issues
ORCID	Open Researcher and Contributor Identification
PGNA	University General Hospital of Alexandroupoli, Associated Partner newly admitted to the Consortium

1. Independent Ethics Advisor

Name:	Chrysanthi
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Ethics Related Experience

2023 - today	Member of the Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence, National Commission for Bioethics and Technoethics, Hellenic Republic https://bioethics.gr/en/news-142/omada-empeirognwmonwn-gia-thn-texnhth-nohmosynh-3098
2019 - today	Ethics Expert, Directorate General for Research and Innovation, European Commission EX2019D366138
2018 - today	Founding member of the HeLaB, a European Research Network formed in 2018 to study, analyse and propose solutions in medicolegal and/or bioethical problems arising in the EU, as its population ages, technology progresses, the economic crisis persists and the member states change, while refugee migration intensifies, and new healthcare or social needs emerge. https://healab.net/
2015 - today	Associate member of the Laboratory for the Study of Medical Law and Bioethics Faculty of Law, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Greece https://medlawlab.web.auth.gr/en/faculty-members/

2. Overview of ethics issues raised by the project activities

2.1. Project activities timing and progress

The project aims to develop a novel wearable diagnostic medical device for point-of-care, operator free, continuous monitoring of patients in high risk for a serious, possibly life-threatening, condition. The device's design and function are based on using AI driven technology, big data sets, extended reality and serious gaming. Its development and testing require single site as well as multicentre clinical trials with the recruitment and participation of healthy volunteers and patients and its use raises various GDPR issues (personal privacy, tracking of movements, possibility of data collection not necessary for its original purpose). The Consortium consists mainly of EU based researchers but there are also participants from a third country involved and finally, the device is meant for commercial use.

Overall, project activities are progressing according to the GA and the approved workplan.

Ethics related procedures have been respected, and the current status of attaining the necessary ethics approvals is as follows:

1.	Beneficiary	1 – ATHENA [Coordinator]
	Committee	ATHENA Research Ethics Committee, Athens, Greece
	Contact	ethics-sec@athenarc.gr
	Submission overview	1) Overall project 2) Clinical Study A protocol with emphasis on personal data management
	Submission date	11.11.2024
	Approval	Approved on 27.11.2024. Protocol no. 50/27.11.2024 With recommendations for further submissions of the remaining clinical study protocols once developed according to the approved workplan.
5.	Beneficiary	9 – TAU [Clinical site in Finland]
	Committee	The Regional Ethics Committee of the Expert Responsibility area of Tampere University Hospital
	Contact	Arvo Ylpön katu 6, 33521 Tampere, Finland Tays Tutkimuspalvelut, Eettinen toimikunta
	Submission overview	Clinical Study A
	Submission date	20.08.2024
	Approval	Approved on 08.10.2024. Extract from the minutes 9/2024. Study initiation is pending till Grant Agreement is amended to add TAU University Hospital as an affiliated entity to TAU.
3.	Beneficiary	10 – LSMU [Clinical site in Lithuania]
	Committee	Kaunas Regional Biomedical Research Ethics Committee, Kaunas, Lithuania
	Contact	A. Mickevičiaus g. 9, LT 44307 Kaunas, Lithuania
	Submission overview	Clinical Study A
	Submission date	15.05.2024
	Approval	Approved on 05.11.2024. Protocol no. BE-2-107/05.11.2024
4.	Beneficiary	11 – GNP [Clinical site in Greece]
	Committee	Ethics Committee, Research Council, General Hospital Papagergiou,
	Contact	Papanikolaou Avenue, TK57010, Thessaloniki, Greece
	Submission overview	Clinical Study A
	Submission date	19.08.2024
	Approval	Approved on 21.08.2024. Protocol no. 2024-B2015-376
5.	Beneficiary	12 – CSS-IRCCS [Clinical site in Italy]
	Committee	Comitato Etico Fondazione Casa Sollievo della Sofferenza

	Contact	Viale Cappuccini, San Giovanni Rotondo, Foggia zipcode: 71043, Italy
	Submission overview	Clinical Study A
	Submission date	17.07.2024
	Approval	Approved on 12.11.2024. Protocol no. 165/CE/2024
6	Beneficiary	13 – HSV [Clinical site in France]
	Committee	Comité de Protection des Personnes Est III
	Contact	CHRU de Nancy - Bâtiment principal - Rez de chaussée - Rue du Morvan 54511 Vandoeuvre-Les-Nancy, France
	Submission overview	Clinical Study A
	Submission date	2.10.2024
	Approval	Approved on 05.11.2024. Protocol no. CPP 24.11.06. Next steps involve submission to: 1) French Data Protection Authority (CNIL) 2) National Agency for Medicines and Health Products (ANSM)

Additionally, the Consortium has admitted the University General Hospital of Alexandroupoli (PGNA) as an Associated Partner to contribute work additional to the GA and the approved workplan. PGNA was included due to expressed interest in and capacity for conducting Clinical Study A on their site and contributing data to the project. Therefore, Clinical Study A has been submitted for approval as follows:

7.	Associated Partner	PGNA [Clinical site in Greece]
	Committee	Ethics Committee, Research Council, University General Hospital of Alexandroupoli
	Contact	University Campus, Alexandroupoli, 68100 Greece
	Submission overview	Clinical Study A
	Submission date	16.12.2024
	Approval	Pending

2.2. Deviations from the ethics issues identified in the Ethics Summary Report

No deviations from the ethics issues included in the Ethics Summary Report have been identified. Project activities in months M01-M12 have not raised any additional specific ethical concerns.

The Consortium has been advised of their obligations to reapply for ethics approvals every time they complete the planning of a new clinical trial. They have also asked for and received advice on how to best recruit study participants in a manner that respects their rights and situation, as indicated during the Ethics Assessment process of the project prior to its obtaining funding.

The Consortium has also been advised that adopting an ethics-by-design approach means, among other things, that they should make a conscious effort to ensure that the final product does not record more information than absolutely necessary for the aims of the project and that all information pertaining to possible threats to personal rights and freedom of participants and future users (should the product be made commercially available) is readily available to them. Additionally, the Consortium has been advised on how

to augment their efforts to make the final product available and affordable to all patients suited to benefit from it.

3. Ethics Analysis

3.1. Overview of the management of project's activities in relation to ethics

The project management, on behalf of the Consortium, complied to the ethics requirements included in the GA by appointing an Independent Ethics Advisor, by providing said Advisor full access to the files of the project, by meeting regularly with the Independent Ethics Advisor and by actively seeking and receiving advice on how to best conduct their work. Collaboration involved all project aspects, focusing on the Clinical Studies planned but also including aspects of testing of prototypes on healthy volunteers during the initial stages of research and development. This way the project management ensured that project activities run on time for this reporting period and are in accordance with the ethics requirements of the GA.

3.2. Activities of the Ethics Advisor

The Independent Ethics Advisor accessed and reviewed all project documents and select relevant recordings of project meetings located in the project's private shared workspace (Teams/SharePoint), participated in regular meetings with the management and select Consortium members, offered advice on the ethics issues identified in the Ethics Summary Report but also on possible ways for the Consortium to adopt an ethics-by-design approach.

3.3. Documents available to the Ethics Advisor

The Consortium has granted full access to the project's private shared workspace (Teams/SharePoint) and made sure that all project materials are readily available for inspection by the independent Ethics Advisor.

3.4. Overview of evidence of ethics compliance

Submission folders and approvals as detailed in the table in Section 5.1, files made available via the shared workspace (Teams/SharePoint) as described in Section 6.3.

3.5. Ethics requirements included in GA and how the Consortium addressed them

The Consortium complied to the ethics requirements included in the GA by appointing an Independent Ethics Advisor, by providing full access to the files of the project, by seeking and receiving advice on how to best conduct their work with emphasis on the vulnerability of study participants, as well as adopting an ethics-by-design approach in their development of the final product before conducting any clinical studies on people.

4. Recommendations to the Consortium

The Consortium needs to speed up the ethics approval processes still pending for some of the sites scheduled to participate in Study A, however the management is aware of the delays and taking all necessary steps to complete the processes.

Planning of Studies B & C needs to be completed in a timely manner and relevant ethics approvals have to be requested anew.

Development of study prototypes, as well as of the finished product need to take into account the need for minimizing data gathering, recruiting an adequate number of study participants. Informing them adequately

about the products strengths and limitations. WP9 includes some steps to ensure that the finished product - should it proves clinically successful - is affordable, easy to use and safe for the prospective customers, however the management has been made aware that a bigger effort should be made in order for the finished product to be available to all those that would benefit from it, not only those that can afford it.

5. Recommendations to the Commission/Executive Agency/Funding Body

None at this point, as no ethical or legal issues that cannot be resolved have been identified. The Consortium adheres to the provisions of relevant regulatory frameworks and the GA, they have asked for and received necessary guidance and they possess the tools and apply the indicated methodologies for completing their project successfully.